

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 6: Visualizing the comprehensive performance of evolutionary multi-objective algorithms applied to problems with two or three objectives (IVEMO: Heatmap)

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Abstract

This tutorial discusses the tool for visualizing the comprehensive performance of evolutionary multi-objective algorithms (IVEMO: Heatmap).

Keywords: JECDM, visualization, interactive tool, experimental verification

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1. Introduction [T]

Source package: (*Projects*) `y2024.gecco2024`

This brief tutorial document showcases how to employ JECDM to visualize a comprehensive performance of evolutionary multi-objective optimization algorithms in 2D and 3D spaces. The employed procedure was originally called ViPEMO and was presented in [1]. It was further implemented as an interactive tool and introduced in [2]. In JECDM, the procedure is renamed to IVEMO-HM, where IVEMO stands for “interactive visualization of evolutionary multi-objective optimization, while HM denotes “heatmap”. The IVEMO is a common prefix for all such tools implemented and is introduced for standardization (note that, however, only the IVEMO-HM method is available in the initial release).

This document does not delve into the details of the employed IVEMO-HM procedure. It is assumed that the interested reader will read [2] first. Instead, this brief tutorial showcases only how to execute the procedure via code.

Before proceeding, let me highlight that the initial release of JECDM provides complete codes for [2] study. They are

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available in the *Projects* module in `y2024.gecco2024` package. The reader is referred to the *Readme.txt* file. In short, one can run the visualization tool for different cases presented in the abovementioned article via the *ExternalLoader* class. Different cases can be run by suitably adjusting the path provided as the main argument. Note that the data to be visualized is already prepared and stored in respective binary files stored in “case” sub-folders. Figure 1 illustrates screenshots of the tool when run for case #6 and #2 for convenience.

2. Generating the data representing a comprehensive performance of the method [T]

Source package: (*Tutorials*) `t1_t10.t6_ivemo_heatmap`

This tutorial shows how to generate the heatmap data representing a comprehensive performance of an evolutionary algorithm for multi-objective optimization. Two central classes can be employed for this purpose: *Heatmap2DProcessor* and *Heatmap3DProcessor* (see `tools.ivemo.heatmap` package in the *EvolutionaryComputation* module). As the names suggest, they are dedicated to 2D and 3D spaces, respectively. These processors are responsible for performing the evolutionary simulations and collecting spatial data on their performance.

The tutorial’s source codes consider a few introductory scenarios. First, they apply the data generation procedure to NSGA-II (`t1_nsgaii` package) and MOEA/D (`t2_moead` package) algorithms. They were applied to a simple DTLZ2 test problem with 2 objectives (Tutorial1(2)a, Tutorial1(2)b files), and 3 (Tutorial1(2)c, Tutorial1(2)d files). Next, the procedure was tuned to illustrate two statistics:

- Expected earliest generation number when the algorithm

(a) MOEA/D, $M = 2$, No. trials in which found (case #6)

(b) NSGA0II $M = 3$, Mean generation when found (case #2)

Figure 1: Screenshots of the IVEMO-HM tool

discovered different parts of the objective space (files with ‘a’ and ‘c’ suffixes).

- The number of trials in which different parts of the objective space were discovered (files with ‘b’ and ‘d’ suffixes).

The expected final renders generated by heatmap processors employed to all considered scenarios are illustrated in Figure 2.

The codes are straightforward. In general, they consist of two major parts. First, the processors are constructed, simulations are executed, and the spatial data is collected. Second, the heatmap 2D (or 3D) is instantiated and run to visualize the data. Although the codes are easy to understand, thus it is up to the reader to get acquainted with them, Listing 1 presenting how to parameterize a heatmap processor is brought here for convenience. The scenario concerns applying NSGA-II to the 2-objective DTLZ2 problem, and the processor is tuned to reveal the expected earliest discoveries of different parts of the objective space. **Important note:** The processor collects the data by inspecting performance vectors of specimens in the current populations stored in the evolutionary algorithm’s specimen container.

The code in Listing 1 starts with instantiating the params container. Then, the most essential field is provided: factory generating an instance of an evolutionary algorithm. The processor will perform simulations many times, using different – independently constructed instances of an evolutionary algorithm tested. They will be derived using this factory object (thus, it is imperative to ensure that the objects constructed are truly independent). Note that the processor will perform test runs one by one in a single thread. Thus, a common random number generator can be used when creating the methods. The presented code

returns NSGA-II applied to solve DTLZ2 with two objectives (note that the processor instantiates internally a *Runner* object to conduct the evolution).

The following field “*notify*” can be adjusted to turn on/off notifications printed to the console by the processor (simulation may take some time; thus, it is recommended to use *true* be able to observe the progression). Next, “*trials*” is another fundamental parameter. It determines the number of test runs that will be executed to measure a comprehensive performance. It is set to 100 by default in this source code. Note that the more test runs, the more credible the final results. However, this number explicitly corresponds to processing time (increases linearly). Next, the “*generation*” field determines the generation limit for each test run (for how many generations the method will be run). Similarly, there is a “*steadyStateRepeats*” field, but it is not used in this example (NSGA-II is a generational method, and the default value of this field is 1; in turn, it suitably adjusted in the scenarios involving MOEA/D).

The three parameters: “*featureGetter*”, “*trialStatistics*”, and “*finalStatistics*” control the processor’s behavior in terms of the final statistics to be produced (the interpretability of the results). First, “*featureGetter*” produces a per-specimen statistic to be stored in the specimens’ corresponding buckets in the discretized objective space when processing a trial. In this example, the “*Generation()*” statistic is used (returns the current generation when the method is called; note that the interface for the features is straightforward – thus, one may easily implement it). Next, “*trialStatistics*” should be supplied. It indicates how to process in-bucket features collected through the test runs (in one test run, for each bucket, its collected features are collected, and a summarizing statistics is produced). In this example, the

“*Min()*” function accounts for the earliest detection time (generation). Finally, “*finalStatistics*” summarizes in-buckets per-trial statistics generated by “*trialStatistics*”. This example employs the “*Mean()*” function. Thus, the processor is ultimately configured to determine the expected (mean) earliest detection times (generations) of different parts of the objective space.

The last four fields tell what part of the objective space (“*_xAxisDisplayRange*”, “*_yAxisDisplayRange*”; from 0.0 to 2.0 in this example) should be discretized and what is the discretization level (“*_xAxisDivisions*”, “*_yAxisDivisions*”; equal 100 in this example). Naturally, the number of divisions should increase along with widening the relevant display ranges to obtain reasonable results. However, increasing the number of test runs then is also required to obtain credible conclusions. Naturally, increasing everything will negatively affect the computational/memory complexity. It is up to the user to find the best context-specific setting for their own experiments. However, the user should be aware that memory complexity increases particularly fast. It is recommended that a Java heap space be set to a meaningful size.

The following two lines create the processor object and execute the processing. During the execution, the ID of a test run being started will be printed into the console. Finally, the last line of code generates refined data structures – using the internal raw data constructed when processing trials – that can be explicitly supplied to *Heatmap2D* object.

Listing 1: Using *Heatmap2DProcessor*

```

// Create Heatmap2DProcessor:
Heatmap2DProcessor.Params pHP = new
    Heatmap2DProcessor.Params();
// Provides instances of tested EA:
pHP._eaFactory = () -> {
5   // NSGA-II applied to DTLZ2:
    AbstractMOOProblemBundle problem =
        AbstractMOOProblemBundle.getBundle(
            Problem.DTLZ2, 2, R);
    return NSGAI.getNSGAI(0, false,
        populationSize, R, problem);
};
pHP._notify = true; // will print
    notifications
10 pHP._trials = trials; // set the number of
    test runs
pHP._generations = generations; // set the
    limit for the number of generations
pHP._featureGetter = new Generation(); //
    returns the feature (generation number
    when captured)
pHP._trialStatistics = new Mean(); // set
    per-trial statistic (mean = average of
    the reported generations)
pHP._finalStatistics = new Mean(); // set
    final statistics (average of per-trial
    results)
15 pHP._xAxisDivisions = xDiv; // set the
    discretization level for x-axis
pHP._xAxisDisplayRange = xDR; // set
    considered bound on the objective space

```

```

(x-axis)
pHP._yAxisDivisions = yDiv; // set the
    discretization level for y-axis
pHP._yAxisDisplayRange = yDR; // set
    considered bound on the objective space
    (y-axis)
Heatmap2DProcessor h2D = new
    Heatmap2DProcessor(pHP);

// Execute processing:
h2D.executeProcessing();
// Generate sorted input data for heatmaps
    (accessible via h2D.getSortedCoords(),
    h2D.getSortedValues())
h2D.generateSortedInputData();

```

References

- [1] M. Kadziński, M. K. Tomczyk, and R. Słowiński, “Preference-based cone contraction algorithms for interactive evolutionary multiple objective optimization,” *Swarm and Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 52, p. 100602, 2020.
- [2] M. Tomczyk and M. Kadziński, “Interactive tool for visualizing the comprehensive performance of evolutionary multi-objective algorithms applied to problems with two or three objectives,” in *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference Companion, GECCO ’24 Companion*, pp. 375–378, Association for Computing Machinery, 2024.

(a) NSGA-II, $M = 2$, Expected min generation when found (Tutorial1a)

(b) MOEA/D, $M = 2$, Expected min generation when found (Tutorial2a)

(c) NSGA-II, $M = 2$, No. trials in which found (Tutorial1b)

(d) MOEA/D, $M = 2$, No. trials in which found (Tutorial2b)

(e) NSGA-II, $M = 3$, Expected min generation when found (Tutorial1c)

(f) MOEA/D, $M = 3$, Expected min generation when found (Tutorial2c)

(g) NSGA-II, $M = 3$, No. trials in which found (Tutorial1d)

(h) MOEA/D, $M = 3$, No. trials in which found (Tutorial2d)

Figure 2: Example final visualizations